

Universität Trier
Fachbereich I – Psychologie
Abteilung Arbeits- & Organisationspsychologie

Masterarbeit

Coaching im Fokus: Eine Meta-Analyse zur Evaluation von Executive Coaching unter Berücksichtigung des Kirkpatrick-Modells

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Verwendeter R-Code zur Auswertung der Ergebnisse:

```
#Analyse vorbereiten und Pakete installieren:
install.packages(c("metafor", "meta", "dplyr"))
install.packages("readxl")
install.packages("car")
install.packages("rmarkdown")
install.packages("metafor")
install.packages("multcomp")

#Pakete Laden:
library(metafor)
library(meta)
library(car)
library(readxl)
library(dplyr)
library(rmarkdown)
library(multcomp)

setwd("/Volumes/T7 Shield/")

#Excel & individuelle Sheets der Excel hochladen:
lev4report <-
read_excel("20242810_MSc_Robin_Hottenbacher_Kodiertabelle_Meta_Analyse.xlsx", sheet
= "Lev4Report")
lev3study <-
read_excel("20242810_MSc_Robin_Hottenbacher_Kodiertabelle_Meta_Analyse.xlsx", sheet
= "Lev3Study")
lev2sample <-
read_excel("20242810_MSc_Robin_Hottenbacher_Kodiertabelle_Meta_Analyse.xlsx", sheet
= "Lev2Sample")
lev1outcomes <-
read_excel("20242810_MSc_Robin_Hottenbacher_Kodiertabelle_Meta_Analyse.xlsx", sheet
= "Lev1Outcomes")
library(effsize)install.packages ("summarytools") library("summarytools")

# Zusammenführen der Daten zu einem Masterdatensatz ----
levels43 <- merge(lev4report, lev3study, all.x=TRUE, by="report_ID")
View(levels43)
levels432 <- merge(levels43, lev2sample, all.x=TRUE, by="study_ID")
View(levels432)
levels4321 <- merge(levels432, lev1outcomes, all.x=TRUE, by="sample_ID")
View(levels4321)
## Create new data object dat from levels4321
dat.all <- levels4321
View(dat.all)

##### META-ANALYSE #####

#3-Level Meta-Analyse:
# Meta-Analyse mit der rma.mv Funktion durchführen
```

```

full.model <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,
  V = o_Varianz_g,
  slab = r_apas,
  data = dat.all, #hier Datensatz einfügen
  random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID, #Hier die beiden Level des
Datensatzen
  test = "t",
  method = "REML")
# Zusammenfassung des Meta-Analyse Modells
summary(full.model)

#Test Vergleich 2-Level Struktur mit 3-Level Struktur:
L3.removed <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,
  V = o_Varianz_g,
  slab = r_apas,
  data = dat.all,
  random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID,
  test = "t",
  method = "REML",
  sigma2 = c(0, NA))

summary(L3.removed)

#ANOVA zum Vergleich eines 3-Level & 2-Level Model:
anova(full.model, L3.removed)

##### UNIVARIAT zur besseren Darstellung der Ergebnisse
#####

#Univariate Analyse:
univariate_model <- rma(yi = o_hedges_g, # Effektgrößen (z.B. Hedges' g)
  vi = o_Varianz_g, # Varianz der Effektgrößen
  slab = r_apas,
  data = dat.all, # Datensatz
  method = "REML") # Restricted Maximum Likelihood (REML) Methode

# Ergebnisse der Meta-Analyse
summary(univariate_model)

reporter(univariate_model)

#Eggers Test Auf Assymetrie:
regtest(univariate_model, model = "rma")

# Forrest Plot
forest(univariate_model,
  main = "Forest Plot",
  xlab = "Effektstärke (Hedges' g)",
  cex = 0.5, # Textgröße der Studientiteln
  refline = 0, # Referenzlinie bei 0
  digits = 2, # Anzahl der Dezimalstellen
  ylim = c(-2, length(univariate_model$yi) + 3))# Erhöhen des vertikalen Bereichs

```

```

# Funnel Plot
funnel(univariate_model,
      main = "Funnel Plot")

# Trim-and-Fill Methode anwenden
trimfill(univariate_model)

##### Moderator
#####

#MODERATORANALYSE: kirkpatrick.model

# Dummy-Variablen für die Kirkpatrick-Ebenen erstellen
dat.all$s_kirkpatrick_Reaction <- ifelse(dat.all$s_kirkpatrick == 1, 1, 0) #
Reaktionsebene
dat.all$s_kirkpatrick_Learn <- ifelse(dat.all$s_kirkpatrick == 2, 1, 0) # Lernebene
dat.all$s_kirkpatrick_Transfer <- ifelse(dat.all$s_kirkpatrick == 3, 1, 0) # Transferebene
dat.all$s_kirkpatrick_Results <- ifelse(dat.all$s_kirkpatrick == 4, 1, 0) # Ergebnisebene

#Dummy-Variable Setting erstellen
dat.all$face_to_face <- ifelse(dat.all$s_setting == 2, 1, 0) # Face to face
dat.all$online <- ifelse(dat.all$s_setting == 1, 1, 0) # online

# Dummy-Variablen für die Transferebene
dat.all$aff_learn <- ifelse(dat.all$s_Learning == 1, 1, 0) # Affektiv
dat.all$kog_learn <- ifelse(dat.all$s_Learning == 2, 1, 0) # Kognitiv
dat.all$psy_learn <- ifelse(dat.all$s_Learning == 3, 1, 0) # Psychomotorisch

# Dummy-Variablen für die Transferebene
dat.all$aff_transfer <- ifelse(dat.all$s_Transfer == 1, 1, 0) # Affektiv
dat.all$kog_transfer <- ifelse(dat.all$s_Transfer == 2, 1, 0) # Kognitiv
dat.all$psy_transfer <- ifelse(dat.all$s_Transfer == 3, 1, 0) # Psychomotorisch

# Dummy-Variablen für die Ergebnisebene
dat.all$results_organ <- ifelse(dat.all$s_Results == 1, 1, 0) # Organisationsebene
dat.all$results_coachee <- ifelse(dat.all$s_Results == 2, 1, 0) # Coachee-Ebene

#Dummy-Variablen Coaching Ansatz:
dat.all$PP <- ifelse(dat.all$s_coaching_approach == 1, 1, 0) # PP
dat.all$GROW <- ifelse(dat.all$s_coaching_approach == 2, 1, 0) # GROW
dat.all$SFC <- ifelse(dat.all$s_coaching_approach == 3, 1, 0) # SFC
dat.all$CBC <- ifelse(dat.all$s_coaching_approach == 4, 1, 0) # CBC
dat.all$MIXED <- ifelse(dat.all$s_coaching_approach == 5, 1, 0) # MIXED

##### ANALYSE KIRKPATRICK EBENEN #####

# Moderatoranalyse ohne Intercept für individuelle Effekte der Kirkpatrick-Ebenen
kirkpatrick_model_no_intercept <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,

```

```

V = o_Varianz_g,
slab = report_ID,
data = dat.all,
random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID,
test = "t",
method = "REML",
mods = ~ 0 + s_kirkpatrick_Reaction + s_kirkpatrick_Learn +
s_kirkpatrick_Transfer + s_kirkpatrick_Results)

```

```

# Zusammenfassung des Modells ohne Intercept
summary(kirkpatrick_model_no_intercept)

```

```

##### META-Regression Anzahl der Sitzungen #####
#####
#####

```

```

# Moderatoranalyse für Sitzungen
Sessions_Mod <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,
V = o_Varianz_g,
slab = report_ID,
data = dat.all,
random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID,
test = "t",
method = "REML",
mods = ~ s_number_of_sessions)

```

```

# Zusammenfassung des Modells anzeigen
summary(Sessions_Mod)

```

```

##### SUBSET KIRKPATRICK EBENEN & Sitzungen #####

```

```

##### Lernebene #####

```

```

#Lernebene:

```

```

Sessions_Learn <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,
V = o_Varianz_g,
slab = report_ID,
data = dat.all, # Verwendet den gesamten Datensatz
random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID,
test = "t",
method = "REML",
mods = ~ s_number_of_sessions,
subset = (s_kirkpatrick == 2)) # Subset für s_kirkpatrick == 2

```

```

# Zusammenfassung des Modells anzeigen
summary(Sessions_Learn)

```

```

##### Transferebene #####

```

```

#Transferebene: Sessions_Transfer
Sessions_Transfer <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,
  V = o_Varianz_g,
  slab = report_ID,
  data = dat.all,          # Verwendet den gesamten Datensatz
  random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID,
  test = "t",
  method = "REML",
  mods = ~ s_number_of_sessions,
  subset = (s_kirkpatrick == 3)) # Subset für s_kirkpatrick == 3

```

```

# Zusammenfassung des Modells anzeigen
summary(Sessions_Transfer)

```

```

##### Ergebnisebene #####

```

```

#Ergebnisebene: Sessions_Results
Sessions_Results <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,
  V = o_Varianz_g,
  slab = report_ID,
  data = dat.all,          # Verwendet den gesamten Datensatz
  random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID,
  test = "t",
  method = "REML",
  mods = ~ s_number_of_sessions,
  subset = (s_kirkpatrick == 4)) # Subset für s_kirkpatrick == 4

```

```

# Zusammenfassung des Modells anzeigen
summary(Sessions_Results)

```

```

##### META REGRESSION KOGNITIVE, PSYCHOMOTORISCHE und
AFFEKTIVE TRANSFEREBENE #####

```

```

#Moderatoranalyse: subset_transfer
# Meta-Analyse-Modell mit den Moderatoren 'kog_transfer' und 'psy_transfer'
subset_transfer <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,
  V = o_Varianz_g,
  slab = report_ID,
  data = dat.all,          # Verwendet den gesamten Datensatz
  random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID,
  test = "t",
  method = "REML",
  mods = ~ 0 + aff_transfer + kog_transfer + psy_transfer)

```

```

# Zusammenfassung des Modells anzeigen
summary(subset_transfer)

```

```
##### META-REGRESSION AFFEKTIVE, KOGNITIVE,  
PSCHOMOTORISCHE LERNEBENE #####
```

```
#Moderatoranalyse: subset_learn
```

```
subset_learn <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,  
  V = o_Varianz_g,  
  slab = report_ID,  
  data = dat.all,          # Verwendet den gesamten Datensatz  
  random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID,  
  test = "t",  
  method = "REML",  
  mods = ~ 0 + aff_learn + kog_learn + psy_learn)  
# Zusammenfassung des Modells anzeigen  
summary(subset_learn)
```

```
##### META REGRESSION EBENE ORGANISATION UND EBENE  
COACHEE #####
```

```
dat.all$results_organ <- ifelse(dat.all$s_Results == 1, 1, 0) # Organisationsebene  
dat.all$results_coachee <- ifelse(dat.all$s_Results == 2, 1, 0) # Coachee-Ebene
```

```
# Meta-Analyse-Modell mit Subset für 's_kirkpatrick == 2'
```

```
subset_results <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,  
  V = o_Varianz_g,  
  slab = report_ID,  
  data = dat.all,          # Verwendet den gesamten Datensatz  
  random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID,  
  test = "t",  
  method = "REML",  
  mods = ~ 0 + results_organ + results_coachee)  
# Zusammenfassung des Modells anzeigen  
summary(subset_results)
```

```
##### MODERATOR COACHING  
APPROACH  
#####
```

```
# Moderatoranalyse ohne Intercept für individuelle Effekte des Coaching Ansatzes
```

```
coaching_approach <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,  
  V = o_Varianz_g,  
  slab = report_ID,  
  data = dat.all,  
  random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID,  
  test = "t",  
  method = "REML",  
  mods = ~ 0 + PP + GROW + SFC + CBC + MIXED)
```

```
# Zusammenfassung des Modells ohne Intercept  
summary(coaching_approach)
```

```
##### LERNEBENE #####
```

```
# Moderatoranalyse ohne Intercept für individuelle Effekte des Coaching Ansatzes
```

```
coaching_approach_learn <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,  
  V = o_Varianz_g,  
  slab = report_ID,  
  data = dat.all,  
  random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID,  
  test = "t",  
  method = "REML",  
  mods = ~ PP + GROW + SFC + CBC + MIXED, # Moderator  
  subset = (s_kirkpatrick == 2)) # Subset für Lernebene
```

```
summary(coaching_approach_learn)
```

```
##### TRANSFEREBENE #####
```

```
# Moderatoranalyse für individuelle Effekte des Coaching Ansatzes  
coaching_approach_transfer  
coaching_approach_transfer <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,  
  V = o_Varianz_g,  
  slab = report_ID,  
  data = dat.all,  
  random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID,  
  test = "t",  
  method = "REML",  
  mods = ~ PP + GROW + SFC + CBC + MIXED, # Moderator  
  subset = (s_kirkpatrick == 3)) # Subset für Transfer
```

```
summary(coaching_approach_transfer)
```

```
##### Ergebnisebene #####
```

```
# Moderatoranalyse für individuelle Effekte des Coaching Ansatzes  
coaching_approach_results  
coaching_approach_results <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,  
  V = o_Varianz_g,  
  slab = report_ID,  
  data = dat.all,  
  random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID,  
  test = "t",  
  method = "REML",  
  mods = ~ PP + GROW + SFC + CBC + MIXED, # Moderator  
  subset = (s_kirkpatrick == 4)) # Subset für Results
```

```
summary(coaching_approach_results)
```

```
##### MODERATORANALYSE SETTING  
#####  
#####
```

```

# Moderatoranalyse für Coachee-Level mit Referenz Setting
Setting <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,
  V = o_Varianz_g,
  slab = report_ID,
  data = dat.all,
  random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID,
  test = "t",
  method = "REML",
  mods = ~ 0 + face_to_face + online)

# Zusammenfassung des Modells anzeigen
summary(Setting)

##### Lernebene #####
setting_learn <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,
  V = o_Varianz_g,
  slab = report_ID,
  data = dat.all,
  random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID,
  test = "t",
  method = "REML",
  mods = ~ 0 + face_to_face + online, # Moderator
'Wenig_Verantwortung'
  subset = (s_kirkpatrick == 2))
summary (setting_learn)

##### Transferebene ##### setting_transfer

setting_transfer <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,
  V = o_Varianz_g,
  slab = report_ID,
  data = dat.all,
  random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID,
  test = "t",
  method = "REML",
  mods = ~ 0 + face_to_face + online, # Moderator
'Wenig_Verantwortung'
  subset = (s_kirkpatrick == 3))
summary (setting_transfer)

##### Ergebnisebene ##### setting_result

setting_result <- rma.mv(yi = o_hedges_g,
  V = o_Varianz_g,
  slab = report_ID,
  data = dat.all,
  random = ~ 1 | report_ID/outcome_ID,
  test = "t",
  method = "REML",
  mods = ~ 0 + face_to_face + online, # Moderator
'Wenig_Verantwortung'
  subset = (s_kirkpatrick == 4))
summary (setting_result)

```

